

Small Bowel Intussusception Causing Intestinal Obstruction in an Adult Patient: A Case Report From the General Hospital of Cancun

José Arturo Estrada-González¹, Rosario Martinez-Victoria², Jorge Armando Basto-Ek³, Pedro Luis Rodriguez-Ramos⁴, Maria De Los Angeles Martinez-Ferretiz⁵, Mariana Ortega-Martinez⁶

^{1,2}4th-Year Resident in General Surgery, Department of General Surgery, Hospital General de Cancún “Dr. Jesús Kumate Rodríguez”, Servicios de Salud del Instituto Mexicano del Seguro Social para el Bienestar (IMSS-BIENESTAR). Programa de posgrado de la Facultad de Medicina, Universidad Autónoma de Yucatán, MEX.

³Radiologist, Hospital General de Chetumal. MEX,

⁴General surgeon, del Hospital General de Cancún, Servicios de Salud del Instituto Mexicano del Seguro Social para el Bienestar (IMSS-BIENESTAR), MEX.

⁵General surgeon, Hospital General de Cancún, Servicios de Salud del Instituto Mexicano del Seguro Social para el Bienestar (IMSS-BIENESTAR), MEX.

⁶Anesthesiologist, Hospital General de Cancún, MEX.

ABSTRACT

This case involves an 18-year-old female patient who presented with a clinical evolution of intestinal obstruction lasting approximately two days. Initially, the condition was managed conservatively; however, the patient showed no clinical improvement. Due to persistent symptoms and CT findings consistent with intestinal obstruction, surgical intervention was decided. Intraoperative findings revealed an enteroenteric intussusception along with a volvulus affecting the same bowel segment. Given the intraoperative conditions, a bowel resection was performed followed by a small bowel anastomosis. The patient had a satisfactory postoperative course and was eventually discharged without complications. Subsequent histopathological analysis was negative for both primary and metastatic neoplasms, indicating a benign condition.

KEYWORDS: adult intussusception, surgery, small bowel, bowel invagination, bowel obstruction, computed

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
28 July 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

INTRODUCTION

Intussusception is defined as the invagination of one segment of the intestine into an adjacent segment. This condition is rare in adults, primarily because it lacks specific symptoms [1]. It can affect both the small and large intestines [2], and may even involve two distinct intestinal segments, as seen in cases of ileocecal intussusception [3]. Most of what is known about this condition comes from its higher prevalence in the pediatric population [4].

The pathophysiology may be attributed to alterations in the peristaltic pattern, which can result from either benign or malignant conditions. Due to its nonspecific clinical

presentation, early diagnosis remains a significant challenge [5].

Given the vague and often non-definitive clinical manifestations, imaging modalities such as ultrasonography are frequently employed for diagnostic purposes. Characteristic sonographic findings—such as the target sign, pseudokidney sign, and crescent-in-donut sign—are similar to those described in the pediatric population. However, as ultrasonography is a highly operator-dependent technique, diagnostic accuracy varies considerably. Studies have shown that operators with basic training achieve a detection rate of approximately 64%,

Small Bowel Intussusception Causing Intestinal Obstruction in an Adult Patient: A Case Report From the General Hospital of Cancun

whereas experienced operators can reach rates as high as 91% [6].

In addition to the aforementioned imaging modality, computed tomography (CT) has become the diagnostic tool of choice for this condition, owing to its high sensitivity—reported to reach 100% in cases where the characteristic 'target sign' is present [7]. CT imaging not only facilitates diagnosis but also enables accurate localization and may help identify underlying etiologies [8].

A systematic review involving 1,902 patients reported that the most frequent anatomical locations of intussusception were colocolic (16.82%), followed by enteroenteric (13.28%), ileocolic (4.89%), and ileocecal (0.78%) [9].

The management of intussusception must be individualized based on the patient's clinical condition, ranging from conservative, non-surgical outpatient treatment to minimally invasive procedures or, when necessary, exploratory laparotomy. In cases of enteroenteric intussusception, initial management may involve simple reduction followed by resection if indicated. In contrast, for colocolic intussusception, primary resection is generally recommended as the initial approach [10].

CASE PRESENTATION

An 18-year-old female with a past medical history of asthma presented to the General Hospital of Cancún due to an acute asthma exacerbation. She was admitted to the Internal Medicine service for medical management. On the third day of hospitalization, the patient developed abdominal pain accompanied by episodes of vomiting with gastro-biliary characteristics.

By the fourth day, the abdominal pain persisted and was now associated with anorexia and nausea. On the fifth day, due to ongoing abdominal pain, absence of flatus and bowel movements, an abdominal ultrasound was requested by the Internal Medicine team. The ultrasound revealed findings consistent with duodenal intussusception and an epigastric abdominal mass of undetermined etiology. Consequently, the General Surgery service was consulted.

On focused physical examination, the only relevant finding was superficial and deep tenderness upon palpation in both hypochondria and the epigastric region. No visceromegaly was appreciated on examination.

Surgical Management and Outcome

Given the nonspecific clinical presentation, an abdominal computed tomography (CT) scan with and without contrast was performed on the fifth day of hospitalization. (FIGURE 1 & 2).

FIGURE 1: Axial CT image showing an apparent “target sign” (arrow).

The imaging revealed a "whirl sign" and the presence of an apparent intestinal loop within another loop, suggestive of intestinal intussusception and associated bowel obstruction.

FIGURE 2: Computed tomography. Coronal projection demonstrating the intussuscepted bowel loop (arrow).

Although a formal radiologist's report was not available at the time, the surgical team interpreted the findings as consistent with mechanical intestinal obstruction, prompting an urgent exploratory laparotomy.

Intraoperatively, approximately 50 mL of serosanguineous fluid was found within the peritoneal cavity. The small intestine, beginning 70 cm distal to the ligament of Treitz, exhibited enteroenteric intussusception with volvulus. A 130 cm segment of the involved small bowel appeared cyanotic, while the remaining 80 cm segment proximal to the ileocecal

Small Bowel Intussusception Causing Intestinal Obstruction in an Adult Patient: A Case Report From the General Hospital of Cancun

valve was viable. A diagnosis of enteroenteric intussusception was confirmed. (FIGURE 3 & 4).

FIGURE 3: Intraoperative image demonstrating volvulated small intestine.

FIGURE 4: Intraoperative image of ischemic small intestine; a segment of small bowel was found with enteroenteric intussusception (arrow).

Surgical management consisted of resection of the affected bowel segment followed by primary end-to-end anastomosis of the remaining viable small intestine.

The patient had an overall favorable postoperative course, with superficial surgical site infection as the only complication. She was discharged on postoperative day eight with outpatient follow-up arranged.

Histopathological Findings.

Histopathological analysis of the resected jejunoleal segment revealed the following:

- No evidence of primary or metastatic neoplasia.
- Acute ischemic-hemorrhagic enteritis, likely secondary to intussusception.
- Surgical margins showed early vascular injury.

DISCUSSION

The clinical course of this patient was consistent with previously reported cases in the literature, characterized by nonspecific symptoms that led to a delay in establishing a

definitive diagnosis. It was not until a clinical reassessment prompted the use of abdominal ultrasonography—due to the persistence of abdominal pain—that intestinal intussusception was initially identified. This was subsequently confirmed by contrast-enhanced abdominal CT, which clearly delineated the site of intestinal obstruction and prompted surgical intervention. Interestingly, the intraoperative findings revealed a different anatomical location of the intussusception than initially suggested by ultrasonography. Nevertheless, the ultrasound played a critical role in raising diagnostic suspicion and guiding further imaging. This case highlights the importance of considering intussusception as part of the differential diagnosis in patients presenting with subacute and poorly localized abdominal pain, even in the absence of classic signs [11].

Fortunately, the etiology of the enteroenteric intussusception in this case was benign, with no evidence of underlying malignancy, which significantly improved the patient's overall prognosis.

CONCLUSIONS

Intussusception remains a rare and intriguing condition within the spectrum of gastrointestinal disorders, particularly when it occurs in adults. As supported by current literature, its diagnosis is often challenging due to nonspecific clinical manifestations. Computed tomography plays a pivotal role in achieving an accurate diagnosis, while histopathological analysis is essential to rule out underlying malignant etiologies.

This case of enteroenteric intussusception contributes to the growing body of evidence and underscores the importance of maintaining a high index of suspicion in patients presenting with vague or subacute abdominal pain. Earlier recognition may lead to timely management and improved outcomes.

REFERENCES

- I. Panzera F, Di-Venere B, Rizzi M, Biscaglia A, et al.: Bowel intussusception in adult: Prevalence, diagnostic tools and therapy. *World Journal of Methodology*. 2021, 11(3):81-87. 10.5662/wjm.v11.i3.81
- II. Alvarez F, Moctezuma P, Pimienta A, et al.: Intususcepción en adultos: todavía un reto diagnóstico para el cirujano. *Revista de Gastroenterología de México*. 2023, 88(4):315-321. 10.1016/j.rgmx.2021.10.010
- III. Ensuncho C, Barguil S, Lara D: Obstrucción intestinal del adulto por intususcepción ileocólica. *Revista Colombiana de Cirugía*. 2024, 39:138-140. 10.30944/20117582.2463
- IV. Lee E, Yang H: Nationwide Population-Based Epidemiologic Study on Childhood Intussusception in South Korea: Emphasis on Treatment and Outcomes.

Small Bowel Intussusception Causing Intestinal Obstruction in an Adult Patient: A Case Report From the General Hospital of Cancun

- Pediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology and Nutrition. 2020, 23(4):329-345. 10.5223/pghn.2020.23.4.329
- V. Muñoz M, Morales J, Cota M: Intususcepción intestinal en adultos. Un desafío para el cirujano general. Revista de la Facultad de Medicina de la UNAM. 2022, 66:30-33. 10.22201/fm.24484865e.2022.65.5.04
- VI. Tempel D, Balk D, Schafer J, et al.: A brief review of diagnostic properties of point-of-care ultrasound for adult bowel intussusception: Making the case for ultrasound. Journal of Ultrasonography. 2023, 23:90-96. 10.15557/JoU.2023.0016
- VII. González C, Baleato S, García J, et al.: Intestinal intussusception in adults: Location, causes, symptoms, and therapeutic management. Radiología (English Edition). 2023, 65(3):213-221. 10.1016/j.rxeng.2022.10.005
- VIII. Gatica C, Hasson D, Díaz I, et al.: Role of imaging in the evaluation of intussusception in adults: A 10-year retrospective study. Radiología (English Edition). 2023, 65(4):291-297. 10.1016/j.rxeng.2020.12.006
- IX. Chand J, Rakesh R, Ganesh M: Adult intussusception: a systematic review of current literature. *Langenbecks Archives of Surgery*. 2024, **409(1)**:235. 10.1007/s00423-024-03429-2
- X. Attoun M, Albalawi S, Ayoub A, et al.: The Management of Intususcepción: A Systematic Review. *Cureus* 2023, 15(11):e49481. 10.7759/cureus.49481
- XI. Tarchouli M, Ait A: Adult Intususcepción: An Uncommon Condition and Challenging Management. *Visceral Medicine*. 2021 37(2):120-127. 10.1159/000507380